

As on 27-02-2020, the following data collection and data entry procedures are recommended in order to add record of potential yield into the knowledge base system.

Steps for data collection:

1. The general way is to find several sources mentioning the potential yield of the crops. Data is search by using the scientific name of the crop to ensure the right crop is taken.
2. The keywords often used to search in the search engine are “scientific name + yield” and “scientific name + potential yield”.
3. A record in the ‘**Potential Yield**’ table will contain a range of values of the potential yield from one or multiple sources.
4. In the source, the lowest value will be recorded as minimum value while the highest as the maximum value. If the mean is not provided, the average of both values will be calculated.
5. If the multiple values are presented, the average of all the values will be calculated. This is usually be the case when the source presents abundant values which are coming from multiple crop variants or lines and a simplified value is required to be obtained.
6. In some cases, gap-filling can be done where the data of a crop can be recorded to other in assumption that they could be the same; however, the record strictly requires an indication that the data is estimated through gap-filling method. ‘Data Flag’ is the field to indicate this process.
7. The steps might vary according to the creativity of data collectors, knowledge capacity and time limitation. In general, the more time spent on the data collection, the more information would be retrieved.

Steps for data entry:

1. There are nine fields to be entered, four of them are meant to be compulsory for every record.

1.1 Crop ID (Compulsory)

- This is referring to the crop common name.
- Choose the **RIGHT** crop name in Crop ID. Since the common name is used in Crop ID, make sure to check the scientific name of the crop in Crop Records. Crop scientific name **MUST** be similar as stated in the data source.

1.2 Location (Compulsory)

- This is referring to the location of the crops. Location **MUST** be recorded according to the region or country or place where the crop is being grown based on the data source.
- Location to be entered **MUST** be ‘Global’ if the location is not mentioned in the reference or if the values of max, mean and min are taken from many resources.
- Multiple locations can be recorded by using the same metadata ID record if there is more than one location stated in the data source.

1.3 Part (Compulsory)

- This is referring to the part of the crop used to calculate the yield.
- Select part ‘Whole’ if the yield is based on the entire part of crops.

1.4 Potential Yield Mean

- This is referring to the average/mean value yield of the crops.
- Make sure the value is rounded at hundreds pace eg. 1245 => 1200, 1452 => 1500.
- The unit of the yield must be in (kg/ha).

1.5 Potential Yield Max

- This is referring to the maximum value yield of the crops stated in the source.
- If there are multiple reliable sources, choose the highest values as 'Maximum' value.
- The unit of the yield must be in (kg/ha).

1.6 Potential Yield Min

- This is referring to the minimum value yield of the crops stated in the source.
- If there are multiple reliable sources, choose the lowest value as 'Minimum' value.
- The unit of the yield must be in (kg/ha).

1.7 Data Flag

- The data flag is given to indicate the methodology used to derive the value.
- In the database the field will show a drop-down menu for selection. The selection are fixed as below:
 - I. Analytical value - Value of analysed result which is directly taken from the source.
 - II. Calculated value - Value derived from a source or multiple sources which are aggregated and processed into one calculated value OR value is calculated for unit conversion.
 - III. Roundup value - Value is being roundup e.g. 2545 -> 2500.
 - IV. Estimated value - Value is estimated from the source hints.
 - V. Gap filled value - Value meant for a crop is derived from the values of its closest relative or species.
 - VI. Source presented value - Value presented in the source.
 - VII. Under revision - Value meant to be revised.

1.8 Notes

- This field is to store other information which is related to the crop itself.

1.9 Metadata ID (Compulsory)

- This field is to link the record to its metadata.
- One **MUST** create a Metadata record in 'Metadata' table before entering Metadata ID.